

Charmonium production as a function of charged-particle multiplicity in pp and p–Pb collisions with ALICE at the LHC

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Abstract

Heavy quarkonium production is an excellent tool to test both perturbative and non-perturbative QCD, as perturbative QCD can describe the heavy quark production process, while the formation of the quarkonium bound state involves non-perturbative aspects. In ultrarelativistic heavy-ion collisions, a deconfined state of QCD matter, made of free quarks and gluons, called quark-gluon plasma (QGP) is expected to be formed. To probe such an environment, the study of quarkonium production is an important tool as the heavy quarks are produced during the initial stage of the collision and experience the entire medium evolution. Surprisingly, in small colliding systems as pp and p–Pb, QGP-like behaviours are observed when selecting high multiplicity events. The physics interpretation of these behaviours remains unclear. However, multiparton interaction is one of the main promising scenarios to explain such observation. Studies of charmonium yields as a function of the event charged-particle pseudorapidity density in pp and p–Pb collision allow one to probe multiple parton interactions in an indirect way. These proceedings present the measurements of quarkonium yields normalised to their average values as a function of the charged-particle multiplicity in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ TeV, performed by the ALICE experiment at the LHC. The corresponding results for the $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ ratios as a function of charged-particle multiplicity are also shown. In addition, J/ψ pair production measurement in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV is discussed.

1 Introduction

The early stages of a heavy-ion collision (A–A) include the formation of hot and dense matter, known as quark-gluon plasma (QGP), consisting of freely moving quarks and gluons. Quarkonia, i.e. charmonia ($c\bar{c}$) and bottomonia ($b\bar{b}$), are expected to probe the whole evolution of the QGP due to the early production of their constituent quarks. Moreover, quarkonia are an excellent tool to test our current knowledge of QCD as heavy quark production takes place during the hard processes of the collision, whereas the quarkonium bound state formation is a soft process. Consequently, quarkonium production is sensitive to both perturbative and non-perturbative aspects of the QCD. The LHC data revealed several unexpected behaviours in small systems (pp and p–Pb collisions) at high multiplicity, e.g. the non-zero elliptic flow of identified hadrons through long-range angular correlation measurements in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV [1] and the enhanced production of multi-strange hadrons in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV [2]. These findings are quite surprising, as they are usually interpreted as signatures of the QGP in A–A collisions. Multiparton interactions (MPI) are one of the main scenarios proposed to explain these observations in small systems. MPIs occur in events in which several parton-parton interactions take place in a single hadron-hadron collision. Several tools can be used to probe MPI with quarkonia, such as double quarkonium production, or quarkonium production as a function of charged-particle multiplicity. The former is a direct probe for MPI, as it is sensitive to double hard parton scatterings. Moreover, it provides information on single quarkonium production mechanisms [3]. However, a large integrated luminosity is required to perform such analysis. On the other hand, the quarkonium production as a function of charged-particle multiplicity is an indirect probe for MPI. It is sensitive to the interplay between soft and hard QCD processes in the event, as quarkonium production is a hard QCD process, whereas the charged particles are usually produced during soft QCD processes.

In these proceedings, the results from pp and p–Pb collisions for the self-normalised quarkonium yields, measured at midrapidity ($|y_{lab}| < 0.9$) or forward rapidity ($2.5 < |y_{lab}| < 4.0$), as a function of the self-normalised

33 charged-particle multiplicity, measured at midrapidity, are discussed. The ratio of the self-normalised $\psi(2S)$ -
 34 to- J/ψ yields as a function of charged-particle multiplicity, in both pp and p-Pb collisions, are also shown.
 35 Finally, the measurement of the J/ψ pair production cross section in pp collisions is presented.

36 2 Experimental setup

37 ALICE (A Large Ion Collider Experiment) is a general purpose detector at the LHC, devoted to heavy-ion physics.
 38 In addition, it has a rich program in small collision systems, such as pp and p-Pb. ALICE is equipped with
 39 18 different sub-detectors, which can be classified into three main categories, according to their usage in the
 40 analyses described below: (i) the muon spectrometer, which reconstructs and identifies the muon tracks at large
 41 rapidity, (ii) the central barrel detectors which reconstruct at midrapidity the primary vertex and charged-particle
 42 tracks, as well as J/ψ in the dielectron decay channel, (iii) global detectors which contribute to triggering, back-
 43 ground rejection and charged-particle multiplicity measurements. More details about the ALICE detector and
 44 its performance can be found in Ref. [4]

45 3 Results

46 3.1 J/ψ pair production in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV

47 The inclusive J/ψ pair production cross section per rapidity unit in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV is presented
 48 in the top panel of Fig.1(a). The results are compared with those for prompt J/ψ production from the LHCb
 49 experiment, performed in a slightly larger rapidity window [5]. A good agreement is observed between the two
 50 measurements within uncertainties. The derived double-to-single J/ψ production cross section results are shown
 51 in the bottom panel of the figure. The ALICE and LHCb results are also consistent within the uncertainties.

Figure 1: (a) Inclusive J/ψ pair production cross section (top panel), and ratio of double-to-single inclusive J/ψ production cross sections (bottom panel), in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. Results are compared with LHCb measurements for prompt J/ψ production [5]. (b) J/ψ self-normalised yields as a function of the self-normalised charged-particle multiplicity [6]. Both quantities are measured at midrapidity. The results are compared with several theoretical models [7–12].

52 3.2 Quarkonium production as a function of charged-particle multiplicity in pp collisions

53 The multiplicity dependence of the inclusive J/ψ production, measured at midrapidity, in pp collisions at
 54 $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV was reported in Ref. [6]. In this work, the J/ψ yields and the charged-particle multiplicity are
 55 normalised to their respective average values obtained in the integrated multiplicity interval. As presented in
 56 Fig.1(b), the self-normalised J/ψ yields at midrapidity exhibit a faster than a linear increase with the increasing
 57 charged-particle multiplicity at midrapidity. The trend of the data is described quantitatively by the following

58 models: the coherent particle production model (CPP) [7], the color glass condensate model (CGC) [9], the
 59 3-pomeron CGC model [8]. The percolation model [10] describes the trend of the data at low multiplicity. The
 60 aforementioned models include initial and final state effects, as well as MPI to describe the behavior of the J/ψ
 61 yields as a function of the event multiplicity. EPOS3 [12] and PYTHIA 8.2 [11] events generators describe
 62 qualitatively a faster than a linear increase but not as strong as in the data.

63 The J/ψ production at forward rapidity as a function of the charged-particle multiplicity measured at
 64 midrapidity in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV has also been reported [13]. The J/ψ self-normalised yields show
 65 an increase compatible with a linear trend within uncertainties. This increase is therefore less rapid than that
 66 of the J/ψ yields measured at midrapidity. The origin of the difference observed for these trends as a function
 67 of multiplicity remains unclear, although the exercise consisting in varying the rapidity range used to select the
 68 charged-particle multiplicity, which is described in Ref. [6], suggests that it is not due to a possible bias when
 69 the hard particle is produced in a jet.

70 In Ref. [14], the self-normalised forward $\psi(2S)$ yields as a function of the charged-particle multiplicity in pp
 71 collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV are presented. The yields show an approximately linear increase with multiplicity
 72 within the uncertainties, see Fig.2(a). The data are compatible with PYTHIA 8.2 calculations [11], both with
 73 and without color reconnection scenario (CR), within the uncertainties (see Ref. [14] for the comparison with
 74 models). In Fig.2(b), the self-normalised $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ ratio is shown as a function of charged-particle multi-
 75 plicity. Measuring the excited-to-ground charmonium state yield ratio allows disentangling possible final state
 76 effects at play in pp collisions, as most of the other effects are expected to cancel in the ratio. The data show
 77 a flat distribution as a function of charged-particle multiplicity. PYTHIA 8.2 calculations suggest a similar
 78 behavior for both $\psi(2S)$ and J/ψ . The $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ self-normalised yields are also compared with the comover
 79 model calculations [15]. The comover model considers the possibility for quarkonia to dissociate due to their
 80 interactions with the final state particles that are comoving with them. The dissociation probability depends
 81 on the size (binding radius) of the particle and the comover density. The comover dissociation has a larger
 82 influence on $\psi(2S)$ with respect to J/ψ , due to its larger binding radius. In the multiplicity range where the
 83 comover model calculations are available, data and model remain consistent within uncertainties.

Figure 2: (a) Inclusive $\psi(2S)$ self-normalised yields, measured at forward rapidity, as a function of the self-normalised charged-particle multiplicity measured at midrapidity, in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and in p–Pb (Pb–p) collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ TeV at forward (backward) rapidity [14]. (b) $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ self-normalised yield ratio, measured at forward rapidity, as a function of the self-normalised charged-particle multiplicity, measured at midrapidity, in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV [14]. Results are compared with predictions from comovers model [10] and PYTHIA 8.2 [11].

84 3.3 Quarkonium production as a function of charged-particle multiplicity in p–Pb collisions

85 Several nuclear effects may influence the production of hadrons in p–Pb collisions, as compared to pp colli-
 86 sions. The gluon shadowing [16] leads to the suppression of quarkonium production in p–Pb collisions with
 87 respect to pp collisions which is described by the modification of the parton distribution functions in the nuc-

88 lei (nPDF) with respect to isolated nucleons. The CGC model [8] considers that at sufficiently high energies,
 89 the gluons interaction probability increases due to their large density, reducing effectively their total amount
 90 (gluon saturation). This scenario can influence both charged-particle and quarkonium production rates. The
 91 fully coherent energy loss model [17] suggests the emission of gluons, induced by the medium, coherently from
 92 partons in the initial state and from the $c\bar{c}$ pair in the final state. On the other hand, the nuclear absorption [18]
 93 and the comovers models [15] influence the production of heavy mesons due to the interaction with final state
 94 particles. The nuclear absorption model predicts the breakup of charmonia due to the interaction with the prim-
 95 ordial nucleus. However, this effect is neglected at the LHC energies, as the time needed to cross the nucleus
 96 by the $c\bar{c}$ pair is much shorter than the charmonium formation time.

97 The multiplicity dependence of the J/ψ self-normalised yields in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ TeV is reported
 98 in Ref. [19]. In this analysis, J/ψ mesons are reconstructed at forward and backward rapidity in the nucleon-
 99 nucleon center-of-mass frame, while the charged-particle multiplicity is measured at midrapidity. The results
 100 show an increase of the yields with increasing multiplicity at both forward and backward rapidity. This increase
 101 is weaker for the yields reconstructed at forward rapidity with respect to the ones reconstructed at backward
 102 rapidity. The trend of the yields are consistent with EPOS3 calculations [12]. The self-normalised yields of
 103 the $\psi(2S)$ as a function of the self-normalised charged-particle multiplicity in p–Pb collisions are presented in
 104 Fig.2(a) and compared to pp collisions. The $\psi(2S)$ yield increases as a function of multiplicity at both forward
 105 and backward rapidity in p–Pb collisions. This increase is compatible with a linear increase, depicted as a
 106 dashed line in the figure, within uncertainties. The $\psi(2S)$ self-normalised yields exhibit a similar behaviour
 107 in pp and p–Pb collisions within uncertainties. In Fig.3(a), the self-normalised yields of $\psi(2S)$, measured at
 108 forward rapidity, are compared with the percolation coupled to comover model [10, 15] and using EPS09 nPDF
 109 parameterizations [16]. The model includes the influence of percolation, where the initial state partons are
 110 represented as strings with a certain transverse size and can interact with each other. In a dense environment,
 111 these strings can overlap, reducing the effective number of strings, and leading to an effective reduction in the
 112 quarkonium production. As described before, the comover model is based on the probability for quarkonia
 113 to dissociate due to their interactions with final state particles. The percolation + comover + EPS09 model
 114 is compatible with the data within uncertainties (the large model uncertainties are dominated by the EPS09
 115 ones). The $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ self-normalised yield ratio at forward rapidity as a function of the charged-particle
 116 multiplicity at midrapidity is presented in Fig.3(b) [14]. The result shows a distribution compatible with unity
 117 within uncertainties. The measurements are compared to the comovers model calculations [15]. Within the
 118 large experimental uncertainties, the results remain consistent with the comover scenario, which suggests a
 119 slightly stronger suppression of the $\psi(2S)$ with respect to J/ψ in the high multiplicity region.

Figure 3: (a) The self-normalised $\psi(2S)$ yield and (b) the self-normalised $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ yield ratio, measured at forward rapidity, as a function of the charged-particle multiplicity, measured at midrapidity, in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ TeV [14]. The $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ yield ratios are compared to the percolation + comover + EPS09 model within the large uncertainties [10, 15, 16], while the $\psi(2S)$ yields are compared to the comover model [15].

120 4 Summary

121 The J/ψ pair production in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV is presented. The result shows a good agreement
122 within uncertainties with similar measurements performed by the LHCb experiment. The J/ψ and $\psi(2S)$
123 self-normalised yields show an increase as a function of the charged-particle multiplicity in pp collisions at
124 $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ TeV. The trend of the data is described by several models
125 which include initial and final state effects, as well as MPI. In the measurement of the $\psi(2S)$ -to- J/ψ production
126 ratios, a similar behaviour for the two states is observed as a function of multiplicity, within uncertainties. The
127 experimental precision on the excited state measurements together with the model uncertainties do not allow
128 one to disentangle possible final state effects at play. The LHC Run 3 will provide higher luminosity, leading
129 to more precise multiplicity-differential measurements, bringing further constraints to MPI modeling.

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